

Structural and Electrical Properties of Oxidic Spinel Containing Zinc, Cobalt, Chromium and Manganese

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X-ray crystallographic study of the system $\text{ZnCo}_{1-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{MnO}_4$ has been carried out with a view to investigating the co-operative influence of other ions like Co^{2+} and Cr^{3+} in the presence of Mn^{2+} (J-T) ion in aiding or hindering the distortion of the spinel lattice. The lattice parameter of the compounds showed that the cubic spinel phase changed to tetragonal when 30% of B-sites were occupied by Cr^{3+} ions. The plot of $V^{1/3}$ vs composition showed a break at the transition region. The electrical resistivity-temperature behaviour obeyed the relation $\rho = \rho_0 \exp(\Delta E/kT)$. The hot probe tests showed that all compounds were p-type semiconductors. The plots of ΔE and mean d_{B-B} distance vs composition showed a break where there was a change in the crystal structure indicating close relationship between crystal symmetry and the mode of conduction.

RECENTLY several mixed metal oxides having general formula XY_2O_4 have been investigated as they exhibit interesting structural, electrical and magnetic properties. In these oxidic spinels, the properties are controlled by the nature of ions, their charge and site distribution amongst 8 tetrahedral (A) and 16 octahedral (B) sites. Several workers¹⁻⁶ have studied the solid solutions by substituting ions at A and B sites. Wickham and Croft⁷ have reported that non distorting ions may be indifferent towards influencing the Jahn-Teller distortion. However, O'Keeffe⁸ observed that the nature of other ions present affect the concentration of Mn^{2+} ions required to produce tetragonal distortion. With a view to investigate the co-operative influence of other ions like Co^{2+} and Cr^{3+} in aiding or hindering the distortion of spinel lattice, the system $\text{ZnCo}_{1-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{MnO}_4$ has been investigated.

Experimental

All the compositions of the system $\text{ZnCo}_{1-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{MnO}_4$ were prepared by mixing component oxides of G. R. quality in appropriate molar proportion. The pellets were prepared by pressing the powder to 10,000 p.s.i. using polyvinylacetate as binder and were heated in air at 900° for 80 hrs. The X-ray diffractometer patterns were taken on Phillips X-ray machine using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation with Ni filter. The electrical resistivity measurements were carried out on LCR Marconi Bridge. V-I characteristics of the sample showed very small non-linearity at low voltage indicating the compounds under investigation were sufficiently homogeneous.

Results and Discussion

The results of X-ray analysis are given in Table 1 and the plot of lattice constant and c/a ratio vs

composition is given in Fig. 1. The system $\text{ZnCo}_{1-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{MnO}_4$ is cubic in the range $0 \leq x < 0.5$ and

Fig. 1. Lattice constant and c/a ratio for the system $\text{Zn}[\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{Mn}]\text{O}_4$.

tetragonal in the range $0.6 \leq x < 1.0$ i.e., the tetragonal distortion is observed when 30% of B-sites are occupied by Cr^{3+} ions. The compound $ZnCoMnO_4$ is cubic with lattice constant $a=8.36\text{\AA}$ which fairly agrees with the value reported by Bongers⁹. The cubic nature of this compound is attributed to the presence of tetravalent manganese at B-site. Recently, by using X-ray spectroscopic technique, Kulkarni¹⁰ has reported the ionic configuration of $ZnCoMnO_4$ as: $Zn^{2+}[Co^{2+}Mn^{4+}]O_4^{2-}$. Our susceptibility measurement also support the above ionic configuration. The last compound $ZnMnCrO_4$ of the system is tetragonal with $a=8.29$ and $c=8.66\text{\AA}$. The tetragonal nature of this compound is due to the presence of Mn^{3+} (J-T) ion at B-site. From Fig. 1 it is observed that the compounds of the system $ZnCo_{1-x}Cr_xMnO_4$ are tetragonal where $x=0.6, 0.8$ and 1.0 with $(c/a-1)=0.035, 0.042$ and 0.044 respectively i.e., the degree of distortion increases with increase in concentration of Cr^{3+} ion. Thus, here the observed distortion of the lattice cannot be said to be due to the presence of distorting ion; as Cr^{3+} is non distorting ion at B-site. According to us, the presence of Cr^{3+} (d^3 configuration) ion which is spherically asymmetric seems to be responsible to co-operate with other ions and brings out the distortion of the cubic symmetry.

A plot of $V^{1/3}$ vs composition showed that the increase was linear and there was a sudden break in the volume at the composition $ZnCo_{0.4}Cr_{0.6}MnO_4$ where there was a change in crystal structure. Such a break has also been reported by Wickham and Croft⁷ in Zn-Ge-Co-Mn oxidic spinel system. An inflexion in the $V^{1/3}$ vs composition curve in the transition region can be explained according to the model of Goodenough and Loeb⁴. At the cubic region the distortion of the individual octahedra is inhibited by the strain energy of the lattice and at the critical composition region co-operative elongation and ordering of the cations at the B-sites, in alternate planes perpendicular to C-axis takes place; producing tetragonal distortion.

The room temperature dc resistivity of the compounds varied from 10^4 to 10^6 ohm-cm. The relationship $\rho = \rho_0 \exp(\Delta E/kT)$ was obeyed in all the compounds. The hot probe tests showed that all the compounds were p-type semiconductors. Taking the average unit cell volume $(8.40\text{\AA})^3$ the value of hole concentration comes out to be 10^{22} per cc. The electrical conductivity σ is given by the relationship,

$$\sigma = p e \mu \quad \dots (1)$$

where p =number of holes per unit volume, e =electronic charge and μ =mobility of holes. The value of mobility comes out to 10^{-9} to 10^{-7} $cm^2/V\text{-sec}$.

The compound $ZnCoMnO_4$ possesses relatively low resistivity ($\rho_{RT}=10^4$ ohm-cm) as compared to $ZnCrMnO_4$ ($\rho_{RT}=10^6$ ohm-cm) indicating the presence of ions of different oxidation states at B-site. From

Fig. 2 it is observed that the resistivity gradually increases in the cubic region ($x \leq 0.5$) and practically remains constant in the tetragonal region ($x \geq 0.6$). As concentration of Cr^{3+} ion increases, the combination

Fig. 2. Plot of d_{B-B} distance, activation energy and isothermal resistivity for the system $Zn[Co_{1-x}Cr_xMn]O_4$.

of Mn^{3+} and Co^{3+} gets stabilized with respect to the combination of Co^{2+} and Mn^{4+} . This kind of behaviour is also reported by Blasse¹ in the system $ZnFe_{2-t}Mn_tO_4$. This leads to the conclusion that in the tetragonal spinels elements having the same oxidation states are present at B-site.

The plots of mean d_{B-B} distance and ΔE vs composition are given in Fig. 2. In the case of cubic compounds $d_{B-B} = \frac{a\sqrt{2}}{4}$ and in the case of tetragonal compounds it has two values, $d_{B-B} = \frac{a\sqrt{2}}{4}$ and $d_{B-B} = \frac{(a^2 + c^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{4}$. A mean value of d_{B-B} distance

is taken for tetragonal spinels. The effect of distortion on the electrical properties can be related to the activation energy. From Fig. 2 it is observed that as d_{B-B} distance increases, the value of activation energy also increases and there is a sudden break in the activation energy where there is a change in the crystal structure. The above discussion leads to the conclusion that a close relationship exists between the crystal symmetry and mechanism of conduction in the system investigated.

The dielectric constant measurements carried out at high temperature did not show any variation from 303K to 673K indicating non-ferroelectric nature of the compounds.

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TABLE I—LATTICE CONSTANT, c/a RATIO, ACTIVATION ENERGY, MEAN d_{B-B} DISTANCE AND ROOM TEMPERATURE DIELECTRIC CONSTANT VALUES FOR THE SYSTEM $ZnCo_{1-x}Cr_xMnO_4$.

x	Structure	a(A)	c(A)	c/a	ΔE (eV)	d_{B-B} distance	ϵ_{RT} at 1 KHz (pF/cm)
0.0	C	8.36	8.36	1.000	0.41	2.956	340
0.2	C	8.38	8.38	1.000	0.43	2.963	275
0.4	C	8.40	8.40	1.000	0.45	2.970	205
0.5	C	8.41	8.41	1.000	0.46	2.973	590
0.6	T	8.27	8.56	1.035	0.45	2.950	435
0.8	T	8.26	8.61	1.042	0.48	2.951	205
1.0	T	8.29	8.66	1.044	0.52	2.964	465

C = Cubic

T = Tetragonal.

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